

Maximum Entropy and Born's Law

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We have argued before that one may obtain the free particle wavefunctions $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ from a maximization of Shannon's entropy $-P(E,t) \ln(P(E,t))$ or $-P(p,x) \ln(P(p,x))$ subject to the periodic dynamic constraints ipx and $-iEt$.

It turns out, however, that $\exp(ipx)$, for example, is orthogonal with respect to different p values and $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$. These properties are usually not associated with maximization of entropy classically. Rather, they are seen as features of linear algebra. As a result, we try to investigate why maximization of entropy subject to the unusual constraints, ipx , $-iEt$, leads to orthogonal wavefunctions (i.e. a kind of probability) and an overlap $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$ describing the overall weight at x . We argue that these features are the basis of Born's Rule.

We extend these ideas to the case of a single particle bound state. In (1), we already argued that is the crest-trough nature of $\exp(ipx)$ which ultimately leads to a crest-trough pattern, albeit an irregular one, for say a quantum oscillator. We further suggested that this accounts for discrete energy levels. We suggest here that orthogonality follows for the same reason. Thus, the orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ for different p values and $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$ = spatial density carry over to a bound state. As a result, $V(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is a wavefunction may be mathematically written as a linear superposition of an orthonormal basis. Overlapping with $W_n^*(x)$ then picks up the corresponding basis piece, and taking the modulus squared yields a full probability, just like $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$. This reasoning, we argue, leads to Born's Rule.

Maximization of Entropy and a Quantum Free Particle

We have argued in previous notes that one may obtain the free particle wavefunction forms $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ from a maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to periodic constraints, i.e.:

Maximize $-P(E,t) \ln(P(E,t)) - iEt P(E,t)$ ((1A)) or $-P(p,x) \ln(P(p,x)) + ipx P(p,x)$ ((1B))

Mathematically, this leads to $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. These have two interesting properties:

- A. $\exp(ipx)$ is orthogonal in p and $\exp(-iEt)$ in E
- B. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$ and $\exp(iEt)\exp(-iEt)=1$

In B, one may at first consider p and $-p$ as representing different directions of motion, but in such a case, how does one interpret E and $-E$. Rather, we consider a movie playing forwards and backwards. In such case, x,t become $-x$ and $-t$ which have the opposite ordering.

One may at first suggest that A and B have nothing to do with maximization of entropy, but are instead features of linear algebra. The forms $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, however, were explicitly obtained from a maximization of entropy subject to periodic constraints. As a result, we ask: Why does one have orthogonality and $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$?

We suggest that the answer is related to the constraints ipx and $-iEt$ and the running of a movie backwards. In classical statistical mechanics, such a consideration does not appear because one uses single particle energy, for example, in a constraint term. A free particle, however, is one that is moving in space and time. It would normally be called a dynamic object and not be associated at all with entropy maximization. As a result, the concept of running a movie forwards and backwards makes sense. This begs the question: Why should entropy be a consideration at all? We argue that entropy is considered because there is an inherent probability associated with each x point. In other

words, each x point carries the same weight or is on the same footing. In such a sense, one may use probability and hence construct a kind of dynamic entropy with dynamic constraints. The entropy result then should be associated with dynamic motion, but at the same time preserve the sense of an equal weighting at each x point. ((1A)) and ((1B)) were only concerned with dynamic features, but if one considers running the movie backwards, one obtains $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(iEt)$ which are complex conjugates because one may take the complex conjugate of ((1A)) and ((1B)) and $P^*(E,t)$ and $P^*(p,x)$ are the probabilities associated with $-ipx$ and iEt .

The maximized form of ((1A)) and ((1B)) for the ipx case is:

$$\ln(P^*) + 1 = -ipx \quad \text{and} \quad \ln(P) + 1 = ipx \quad \text{Adding yields: } \ln(P^*P) + 2 = 0$$

This means that P^*P carries no p,x information, i.e. is essentially a constant. Thus, maximization of entropy with dynamic constraints, which may be linked to running a movie backwards and forwards, is associated with the fact that each x point (and each t point) has the same weight. Similarly, the orthogonality condition A shows that for $P^*(p_1)P(p)$ there is no balance in momentum here and no equal weighting at each x point. Integrating $P^*(p_1,x)P(p,x)$ yields 0 as there can be no overall weight factor obtained because each p yields its own weight through the integral over x , $P^*(p,x)P(p,x)$.

As a result, we argue that maximization applied to the dynamic case of a free particle, together with considerations of running a movie backwards and forwards, leads to the two fundamental conditions A and B which would normally be associated strictly with linear algebra and not entropy.

The Single Bound State

We next ask: What happens if one considers a particle in a potential well $V(x)$. It is no longer a free particle, but rather one may create a kind of ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$'s, instead of many particles with different p 's as in the classical statistical mechanical case. In other words, one may use conservation of average energy, i.e.:

$$\left(\sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ p p/2m \ \exp(ipx) \right) / \left(\sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \right) + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

Maximization of entropy has been used to establish the form $\exp(ipx)$. Does one need to use a second maximization of entropy to describe a bound state? ((2)) shows that solutions exist simply using conservation of energy, which is required, and so there seems to be no need to seek extra maximization of entropy. Maximization of entropy seems to be used when one wishes to remove all unnecessary information, i.e. one maximizes the number of states because there is no extra information which yields preference of one state over another. Conservation of energy, however, is not a piece of information which may be removed. One may see that ((2)) may be rewritten as:

$$-.5 \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + VW = EW \quad ((3))$$

((3)) may be mathematically solved to yield a set of orthogonal energy eigenfunctions with E being discrete and not continuous. This orthogonality is reminiscent of A. In fact, in (1) we suggested that is the crest-trough nature of $\exp(ipx)$ which carries over into the solution of $W(x)$, although the crests-troughs are now irregular. One needs to have the wavefunction decrease outside classical turning points and have a crest-trough pattern inside. This leads to discrete E_n values, but also to orthogonality of $W^*(n_1,x) W(n_2,x)$, where n_1 and n_2 are different energy levels, analogous to $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ yielding 0 when integrated.

Thus, $W^*(n,x)W(n,x)$ yields the spatial weight of each x point (like $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ did) and $W^*(n_1,x) W(n_2,x)$, integrated over x , yields 0, showing that one does not have balanced states. Mathematically, the integration yields 0 because of the crest-trough behaviour. A simple example is the ground state of an oscillator compared to the first excited state which has opposite parity.

Symmetry considerations when creating the first excited state show that its overlap with the ground state (i.e. integration over x) is 0.

Born's Rule

We argue that the notion of overlap, i.e. $W_1^*(x)W_2(x)$ ultimately follows from the maximization of entropy for a dynamic free particle. Classically, one does not see such a thing because one does not consider a dynamic system, i.e. one moving in one direction, as an equilibrium system. Rather, it is assigned to classical mechanics and not classical statistical mechanics. We suggest that it is the maximization of entropy, linked with dynamic constraints ipx and $-iEt$, and the notion of running a film backwards, which leads to $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$, i.e. the weight of each x , and the orthogonality for different p values. It seems that it is the periodicity of $\exp(ipx)$ which leads to orthogonality if p is changed as an increase in a hump at one place must be compensated for at another.

As a result, given an arbitrary function $F(x)$, say $V(x)W(x)$, one may expand this in a series using a basis of $W_n(x)$ functions, i.e. eigenfunctions of some Hamiltonian. This is very much a linear algebraic process, but the notion of the integral of $W_n^*(x)V(x)W(x)$ seems to give a weight associated based on the maximization of entropy for dynamic constraints given above. Given this weight, one takes: $\text{weight}^* \text{weight} \int W_n^*(x)W_n(x) dx$, but the integral is 1 if W_n is normalized and so $\text{weight}^* \text{weight}$ is the overall probability weight (like $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$).

Conclusion

In conclusion, although linear algebra is usually considered the reason for orthogonality of energy eigenfunctions in quantum mechanics, or of $\exp(ipx)$ for a free quantum particle, we argue that these results follow from maximization of entropy. In particular, one maximizes a dynamic entropy for a free particle using the dynamic constraints ipx $P(p,x)$ and $-iEt$ $P(E,t)$. These lead to $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, but considerations of a moving running forwards and backwards show that $P^*(p,x)P(p,x)=1$, i.e. gives the overall weight for x or t . Integrating $P^*(p,x)P(p_2,x)$ yields 0 because there is no balance. Thus, one does not need linear algebra to explain why $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ is a weight of x and $W_{n1}^*(x)W_n(x)$ integrates to 0. We argue that these ideas carry over to the bound state case, where one again has a crest-trough pattern, albeit an irregular one now.

As a result, if one has an arbitrary function $V(x)W(x)$, one may calculate the overlap with $W_n(x)$, an energy eigenfunction of some Hamiltonian for example. This yields an overall weight and then using the $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ weight at x to obtain overall probability one may integrate: $\text{weight}^* \text{weight} \int dx W_n^*(x)W_n(x) = \text{weight}^* \text{weight}$ which is Born's Rule. As a result, we argue that Born's rule does not appear in classical statistical mechanics because one does not maximize entropy for a dynamic system, i.e. one moving in one direction, subject to dynamic constraints which may be linked with playing a movie forwards or backwards and lead to a product rule $P^*(p,x)P(p,x)$ for finding an overall weight at x .

Reference

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Discrete Bound Energies and the Free Particle $\exp(ipx)$ (preprint, zenodo, 2023)